

THE IMPORTANCE OF BEES IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract: Nowadays, beekeeping is one of the important sectors developing in our Republic. The importance of bees in agriculture is very great, and about 80% of plants known to mankind form buds and fruits and seeds as a result of cross-pollination. As a result of bees pollinating plant flowers from the outside, they create conditions for improving their species and creating high-yielding varieties, and increase their yield to a certain extent. A number of laws and resolutions have been adopted in our Republic to develop beekeeping, which are of great practical importance in the development of this sector.

Keywords: Bees, Livestock, settlement, farm, pollination, plant, insects, territory, bee breeds.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПЧЕЛ В СЕЛЬСКОМ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕ

Аннотация: В настоящее время пчеловодство является одной из важных отраслей, развивающихся в нашей республике. Значение пчел в сельском хозяйстве огромно: около 80% известных человечеству растений дают плоды и семена в результате перекрестного опыления. В результате опыления пчелами цветков растений извне создаются условия для улучшения здоровья их вида и создания высокоурожайных сортов, в определенной степени повышается их урожайность. В целях развития пчеловодства в нашей республике принят ряд законов и постановлений, имеющих большое практическое значение в развитии этой отрасли.

Ключевые слова: Пчелы, Животноводство, поселение, ферма, опыление, растение, насекомые, территория, породы пчел.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the development of beekeeping, one of the most important branches of animal husbandry in the world, is of great importance. In our republic, the beekeeping sector is one of the highly profitable sectors of agriculture. Our republic is one of the historical centers for the breeding and care of bees, and its sunny nature plays an important role in the development of the sector. In recent years, a number of measures have been taken to radically improve the management system of the beekeeping sector and organize it on a scientific basis, increase the efficiency of beekeeping operations, further increase the volume and types of honey product production, introduce modern technologies for honey processing, and increase the export potential of the sector. Another invaluable service of bees is that they increase the yield of various crops by pollinating plant flowers. About 80% of plants known to mankind on Earth develop buds and produce fruits and seeds as a result of cross-pollination. Four-fifths of all plants that require cross-pollination are pollinated by insects, and the benefits of bees to humanity are incomparable.

In recent years, a number of measures have been adopted in our Republic to ensure food security for the population, including increasing the production of quality honey products.

In particular, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-3327 dated October 16, 2017 on measures to further develop the beekeeping sector in our Republic, as well as the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-239 dated June 12, 2023 on the development of the beekeeping sector in the Republic based on modern

scientific approaches, the creation of more favorable conditions for the effective organization of beekeeping activities, and the widespread introduction of the practice of pollination of agricultural crops with bees to increase their productivity serve as a program for the rapid development of the beekeeping sector. "The program for the development of the livestock sector and its branches in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 sets out the following tasks: to organize breeding work in beekeeping sectors on a scientific basis, to increase the efficiency of beekeeping operations, to further increase the volume and types of honey products, to introduce modern technologies for honey processing, to increase the export potential of the sector, and to increase the volume of honey products from 25 thousand tons to 52.5 thousand tons.

The natural climatic conditions of our republic are very favorable for growing vegetable crops and raising bee colonies based on rapid technology. During the cotton flowering period, more than one million bee colonies can be raised in one cotton field. As a result of external pollination of plant flowers by bees, it creates conditions for improving the health of their species and creating high-yielding varieties, and to a certain extent increases their yield.

Research objective: To study the scientific and practical research, decisions and their importance in agriculture in the development of beekeeping in our republic.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The importance of bees in pollination has long been known. Many scientists have been engaged in the issue of plant pollination. They have proven that bees participate in pollinating melon crops and fruit trees, increasing their yield by 4-5 times. The issue of increasing yields with the help of bees and other complex measures is also being given importance in all regions of the country.

According to scientists, pollination of plants with the help of bees increases the yield of alfalfa by 180-250%, sunflower by 40-50%, black wheat by 1.5 times, cabbage, turnip, onions by 30-40%, and flax by 27%. One of the main conditions for achieving high pollination indicators is the location of the apiary close to the pollinated area and the absence of obstacles in the way of bees flying to this place. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is advisable to place pollinator colonies in cotton and rice fields in smaller groups (40-50 families) at a distance of 450-500 meters from each other. In gardens, this distance is reduced to 200 meters. If the area is rectangular or circular, it is better to place the colonies in the center of the massif. If it is elongated, they are placed one after the other with an interval of 800-1200 meters. In the garden, it should not exceed 200 meters. Bees play an important role in pollinating plants compared to wild insects. Bees live in large numbers (50-80 thousand), have the ability to accumulate large reserves of honey and pollen, and visit a large number of flowers to pollinate them. A worker bee lands on 100-150 flowers during each flight to the flowerbed, while a strong colony of bees lands on 50-60 million flowers of sunflowers, clover, melon crops, fruit trees and other plants. During their visit to the flowers, bees successfully pollinate plants by carrying 3-5 million pollen grains on their bodies. Honeybees perform 80-90% of pollination, while wild insects pollinate up to 10-20%.

In beekeeping, there are bee breeds adapted to the natural and climatic conditions of each region.

Bee breeds. It is widespread in our republic and adapted to the climate. Therefore, keeping this breed of bees in households is much more advantageous than other breeds of bees. In our country, along with the local breed of bees that produce a lot of honey, there are also the "Kungir Tog" bees, "Yellow Caucasus" bees, "Carpathian" "Ukrainian Chuli" "Italian" "Central Russian", "Karnika" and Yugoslav breeds. The bee breed, which is called the Carpathian by origin, has been

a bee breed suitable for the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan for a century, and since it has been a bee breed suitable for the climatic conditions of Uzbekistan from the last hundred years to the present day, bees of this breed and their descendants have been kept and bred in all regions and districts of the Republic of Uzbekistan for a century.

CONCLUSION

The importance of royal jelly: Royal jelly has a beneficial effect on the nervous, cardiovascular, genitourinary, digestive, joints and bones, muscles, lungs and respiratory systems. Preparations for the treatment of a number of diseases are produced from royal jelly. Royal jelly improves metabolism, is used against obesity or weight loss. It increases the human body's resistance to infectious diseases, improves the functioning of the endocrine glands. It has a good effect in the treatment of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular insufficiency. Due to the multifaceted nature of royal jelly and its different effects on various systems of the human body, this drug should be taken only on the recommendation of a doctor.

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